

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

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CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF THE POEM “DEFEAT” BY KAHLIL GIBRAN

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Abstract. *This article focuses on metaphors, their types, how they are used in our daily lives, and the power and the importance of metaphors in poetry by analyzing poem “Defeat” written by Kahlil Gibran.*

Key words: *metaphor, practical, verbal portrait, comparison, cognitive structure, conceptual metaphors, orientational metaphors, ontological metaphors.*

The growth of interest in metaphor has been stimulated by the increase in its use in our everyday life and it attracted many scientists and thinkers.

There are a lot of concepts about metaphors since last six decades, and the scientists and thinkers claim that, the metaphor is extremely practical. It can be used as a tool of description and explanation in any field: in psychotherapeutic conversations and in conversations between airline pilots, in ritual dances and in programming languages, in art education and in quantum mechanics. Metaphor, wherever we encounter it, always enriches the understanding of human action, knowledge and language.

The sphere of expression of emotions and emotional pressure introduces an element of artistry into everyday speech, and with it a metaphor. “A metaphor often contains an accurate and vivid description of a person. This is a verdict, but not a judicial one. The metaphor does not penetrate either the dossier or the questionnaire. In the column about Sobakevich’s special features, “bear” cannot be placed - the metaphorical “container” of his special features. But for the actor playing the role of Sobakevich, this metaphor is important: instructions for creating an artistic image can be figurative. Metaphor is also effective in a verbal portrait of the wanted person. After all, recognition is made not only by moles and tattoos, but also by the image stored in memory. This is art. A metaphor, if it is successful, helps to reproduce an image that is not given in experience.”

There are a lot of arguments about usage of metaphors between English rationalist philosophers, who examined metaphorical provisions in scientific discourse, and romantic thinkers and scientists. While English rationalist

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philosophers were negative about the use of metaphor in conveying information, since its unclear and vague, romantic thinkers and scientists perceived metaphor as something that could not be avoided.

Metaphor not only forms an idea of an object, it also predetermines the way and style of thinking about it. In the same way, in practical speech, having given impetus to the semantic process, the metaphor is gradually erased and ultimately loses an image, which is replaced by the concept, in other words, the meaning of the word. In art, on the contrary, artistic thought strives for metaphor, starting from the image. In this sense, metaphor is a tool and at the same time the fruit of poetic process.

The connection of metaphor, with fantasy, as well as its imagery, opened the way for the use of metaphor in modern painting, theater and cinema, etc. Metaphor is designed to create an image of an object that would reveal its latent essence. A metaphor deepens the understanding of reality, a symbol takes us beyond its limits.

The essence of comparison is to liken one object to another object, and the essence of metaphor is to reveal a constant feature of an object with the help of another object or concept. If the comparison depends on time, that is, at that moment he looked like a bird, the metaphor is not delimited by time; you are now a tiger. “A dispute about similarity is a dispute about impressions. A dispute about the choice of metaphor is a dispute about the true essence of the subject”

If earlier a metaphor was defined as an abbreviated comparison, but now Arutyunova proves that, along with the sign of comparison, the metaphor also abandons the basis of comparison, for example: Sobakevich is clumsy, ponderous and clubfooted like a bear, here Sobakevich is compared to a bear, because he repeats with his clubfoot and clumsiness bear quality. If you use a metaphor instead of a comparison, it will sound like this: Sobakevich is a bear. “The metaphor is figurative, the metaphor is “a court verdict without trial.” The verdict is without motivation, without explanation.” Although this is not a judicial (literally) sentence, this is how it is perceived.

There are different types of metaphors, which are used in our daily life. We even don't know the types of metaphors, or we don't pay attention to the type of metaphor, when we use them. But there are several types of metaphors, for instance, orientational metaphors. We call it an orientational metaphor since in is associated with orientation. For example: “top-bottom”, “inside-outside”, “central-peripheral” and etc. Everything good that happens to a person in most often described through the metaphor of the top, and now, someone is at the top of bliss and feels on the rise. And what bad things happen to us is described through metaphors from below. For

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instance: the mood has dropped, or someone has come down with a cold and slipped from A's to C's and etc.

To understand actions, events or activities, there is another group of metaphors, ontological ones. These types of metaphors serve different purposes, and different kinds of metaphors reflect different purposes. The MACHINE metaphor creates an idea of the mind as a device that is characterized by on-off phases, efficiency, production capacity, which has an internal mechanism, an energy source, which is characterized by certain operating conditions. The FRAGILE OBJECT metaphor is not so rich. It allows us to talk only about the psychological strength of a person. Nevertheless, some part of the experience associated with the inner world of a person can be understood in terms of both metaphors.

Don't broke down. It's broken' (THE SHOWER IS A MACHINE).

Not cracked up. Yun moved (literally, cracked)' (THE MIND IS A FRAGILE OBJECT).

But these two metaphors do not highlight the same thing in experience. When a car breaks down, it simply stops working. When a fragile object breaks, parts fly apart, possibly with dangerous consequences. Thus, when someone goes crazy and becomes violent or violent, the appropriate expression is Not cracked up. On the other hand, when someone becomes lethargic and unable to act for psychological reasons, we are more likely to say Not broke down. Such metaphors are so accurate and natural, even we perceive them as direct descriptions, as descriptions that are used not in a figurative sense, but in a literal one.

There are some other examples and by analyzing poem "Defeat" which is written by Kahlil Gibran, we can see the influence of metaphor in poetry, or even in literature and our daily life at all.

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